

A Lexico-Semantic Analysis of Nigerianisms in Lola Shoneyin's *The Secret Lives of Baba Segi's Wives*

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Abstract

Studies of Nigerianisms are abundant in both literary discourse and everyday communication, with the potential of Nigerian literature serving as empirical evidence for the codification of Nigerian English. This study examines Nigerianisms in Lola Shoneyin's *The Secret Lives of Baba Segi's Wives*, a novel that depicts the socio-cultural setting of Nigeria and foregrounds the use of localised lexical forms. The study relies on Adegbija's (1989) and Bamiro's (1994) analytical taxonomy for linguistic categorisation of lexicosemantic features in Nigerian English to interrogate the novel's literary deployment of non-standard lexical items. Through the qualitative analysis of purposively selected twenty-one key excerpts, we identify and categorise four primary lexico-semantic strategies: neologistic coinage, semantic extension, translation equivalents (calques), and direct lexical borrowing. These forms extend meaning by adapting English lexical items to encode culturally specific concepts, social relations, and indigenous epistemologies. The analysis further demonstrates that Nigerianisms operate systematically rather than idiosyncratically, functioning as patterned linguistic resources within literary discourse. Thus, Nigerianisms constitute empirically grounded evidence of the structural and semantic evolution of Nigerian English. The study concludes that literary texts provide valuable evidence for understanding the lexico-semantic dynamics of localized English varieties.

Keywords: Nigerian English, Nigerianisms; lexico-semantic variation; World Englishes, lexical borrowing

Introduction

The global spread of English has resulted in the emergence of multiple localised varieties shaped by distinct sociocultural environments, a central concern within World Englishes scholarship (Kachru, 1985; Schneider, 2007). In postcolonial contexts such as Nigeria, English has undergone sustained processes of adaptation, resulting in a variety that reflects local communicative needs, cultural practices, and social structures. One of the most salient features of this adaptation is the emergence of Nigerianisms, which are lexical items and semantic

patterns that encode culturally specific meanings within the English language. This study examines Nigerianisms in *The Secret Lives of Baba Segi's Wives* as instances of lexico-semantic innovation within Nigerian English. The primary aim is not to evaluate these forms against external standards, but to analyse how they function systematically as meaning-making resources within a literary text. While the findings may have broader implications for discussions of Nigerian English, the focus of this study remains on the structural and semantic properties of Nigerianisms as they occur in context.

Nigerianisms typically manifest through processes such as semantic extension, lexical borrowing, calquing, and coinage. These processes enable speakers and writers to adapt English to express indigenous concepts, social relations, and culturally embedded experiences that are not adequately captured by Standard British English. Rather than representing random deviations, such forms often exhibit patterned usage and shared interpretive norms within Nigerian speech communities. As such, they provide a useful entry point for examining how meaning is extended and restructured in localised varieties of English. Literary texts offer a particularly rich site for this kind of analysis. Writers often draw on everyday linguistic practices to construct dialogue, character identity, and social context, making literature a valuable resource for observing naturally occurring language variation in stylised form. In *The Secret Lives of Baba Segi's Wives*, the use of dialogue across characters of different educational and social backgrounds creates a layered representation of Nigerian English. The novel's incorporation of localised lexical forms is therefore not incidental but integral to its representation of social interaction and cultural reality.

Despite extensive studies on Nigerian English and numerous critical readings of Shoneyin's work, relatively little attention has been paid to the systematic analysis of Nigerianisms at the lexico-semantic level within literary texts. Existing scholarship has tended to prioritise phonological, syntactic, or thematic concerns, often treating language as a transparent medium rather than as an object of structured analysis. This creates a gap in understanding how localised lexical forms operate as patterned linguistic features in literary discourse. This study addresses this gap by identifying and analysing selected Nigerianisms in the text using a lexico-semantic framework. Specifically, it seeks to (i) classify the types of lexico-semantic processes underlying these forms, and (ii) demonstrate how they function as systematic linguistic resources rather than isolated stylistic choices. Through this approach, the study contributes to a more focused understanding of how Nigerian English operates at the level of meaning and lexical structure within literary contexts.

Synopsis of *The Secret Lives of Baba Segi's Wives* by Lola Shoneyin

The Secret Lives of Baba Segi's Wives centres on the household of Baba Segi, a wealthy Nigerian man with four wives and several children. The narrative unfolds within this polygamous family, where the arrival of the fourth wife, Bolanle, disrupts the existing domestic structure. Unlike the other wives, Bolanle is educated and reserved, and her inability to conceive becomes a central source of tension in the household. As the story progresses, interpersonal conflicts among the wives intensify, driven by rivalry, suspicion, and competition for status and security. Baba Segi's concern over Bolanle's childlessness leads to medical intervention, which ultimately exposes hidden truths about the paternity of the children in the family. This revelation destabilises the household and forces a reconfiguration of relationships among its members.

The novel is largely driven by dialogue and character-specific narration, with each voice reflecting different social, educational, and cultural backgrounds. This variation in speech

provides a rich representation of Nigerian English in use, particularly in the deployment of Nigerianisms. Expressions related to kinship, food, social hierarchy, and belief systems are embedded in everyday interactions, making the text a valuable resource for examining lexico-semantic variation. As such, the novel offers a functional linguistic context in which localised lexical forms can be identified, classified, and analysed

Nigerianism as a Lexico-Semantic Phenomenon

The concept of Nigerianism has been employed to describe lexical items, expressions, and semantic patterns that are either unique to Nigeria or carry meanings shaped by Nigerian sociocultural contexts (Banjo, 1996; Adebija, 2004). Nigerianisms may take the form of coinages (go-slow), semantic extensions (dash), calques (senior brother), or direct borrowings from indigenous languages (agbada, suya). These processes extend meaning by either expanding the semantic range of existing English words, structurally translating indigenous expressions into English, or introducing culturally bound lexical items that encode meanings absent in Standard English. They are often marked as “non-standard” when measured against exonormative English models, yet they perform crucial communicative and cultural functions within Nigerian discourse.

While several studies have catalogued Nigerianisms in media discourse, everyday communication, and educational contexts, they are frequently treated as informal or peripheral phenomena rather than as foundational elements of NE’s lexical architecture. This marginalisation obscures their potential role as building blocks for codification, particularly when such forms demonstrate recurrence, stability, and broad intelligibility within Nigerian speech communities. Scholars have shown that Nigerian literature, in particular, systematically incorporates indigenous discourse patterns, idioms, and semantic structures into English (Nwachukwu-Agbada, 2007). Unlike spontaneous speech data, literary language is deliberately crafted, revised, and circulated, allowing recurring Nigerianisms to gain visibility, legitimacy, and interpretive stability. However, much of the existing literary-linguistic scholarship focuses on stylistics, pragmatics, or ideological concerns, with relatively little sustained attention to the lexico-semantic implications of literary Nigerianisms for NE codification.

Perspectives on The Secret Lives of Baba Segi’s Wives

While previous studies on the novel have focused on themes such as gender, power, and polygamy, relatively little attention has been paid to its linguistic features, particularly its use of Nigerianisms. This present study shifts focus from thematic analysis to a systematic examination of lexico-semantic patterns in the text. Critics consistently recognise the novel as a social text that resists reductive moral judgments through its portrayal of marital arrangements, female agency and patriarchal authority. However, while the thematic and ideological dimensions of the novel have been extensively examined, its linguistic texture, particularly its lexico-semantic Nigerianisms, has received comparatively limited focused attention.

One of the most influential critical readings of the novel is provided by Moolla (2017), who cautions against simplistic condemnations of polygamy in postcolonial African contexts. Rather than presenting plural marriage as an unequivocal site of female victimhood, Moolla argues that Shoneyin’s narrative reveals its paradoxical function as a source of material stability and social protection for women operating within precarious economic conditions. Just as Soyinka deploys satire to portray societal ills on the African continent (Adenigbo & Alugin, 2020), the novel exposes the contradictions of a household governed by a seemingly tyrannical

patriarch whose authority nevertheless provides a form of security unavailable in a harsher social landscape. By situating the novel within historical, religious, and socio-anthropological discourses, Moolla reframes polygamy as a rational response to global and local pressures. This reading establishes the novel as a text that negotiates, rather than resolves, moral ambiguity.

Building on the critical interrogation of polygamy, Nyuykighan (2025) adopts a more explicitly feminist lens to foreground the oppressive mechanisms embedded within plural marriage. This study draws attention to the emotional, psychological, and physical toll polygamy exacts on women, including rivalry, subjugation and reproductive anxiety. Unlike readings that emphasise strategic female accommodation, Nyuykighan's analysis highlights the covert violence sustained within the household and challenges romanticised cultural representations of polygamy. By emphasising women's lack of autonomy and the normalisation of suffering, the study reinforces the novel's critique of patriarchal institutions, advocating for marriage as a matter of choice rather than obligation. While methodologically qualitative and interpretive, this approach underscores the novel's role as a vehicle for feminist intervention.

Relatedly, Eze (2015) approaches the novel from a theoretical standpoint that foregrounds empathy as both a literary strategy and a social ethic. Rather than framing Shoneyin's feminism in confrontational terms, Eze proposes "feminist empathy" as a lens through which the novel unsettles entrenched cultural norms. This perspective situates *The Secret Lives of Baba Segi's Wives* within a tradition of contemporary African women's writing that prioritises emotional insight as a means of social critique. Eze's contribution is significant in shifting attention from overt resistance to subtler forms of narrative persuasion, though it remains primarily concerned with ethical and ideological implications rather than linguistic form.

Other critics have focused on the novel's characterisation strategies, particularly its portrayal of masculinity. Idowu-Faith (2016), employing a critical stylistics framework, examines how linguistic choices shape male characterisation in the text. This stylistic attention marks an important departure from purely thematic readings, suggesting that language plays a crucial role in encoding ideological meaning. However, the study's emphasis remains on character politics rather than on the broader implications of Nigerianized lexico-semantic forms for the evolution of Nigerian English.

Across these studies, a shared consensus emerges: Shoneyin's novel is a socially engaged text that interrogates gendered power, challenges patriarchal myths, and destabilises simplistic narratives of oppression and liberation. Nonetheless, existing scholarship tends to privilege ideological critique, feminist theory, and narrative ethics, often treating language as a transparent medium rather than as an object of systematic analysis. Where linguistic issues are addressed, they are typically subsumed under stylistics or characterisation, leaving unexplored the patterned use of Nigerianisms as culturally and socially meaningful lexical choices.

This gap is particularly striking given the novel's pronounced polyvocality and its deliberate differentiation of characters through language. The recurrent deployment of localised lexical items and culturally specific expressions suggests that Shoneyin's text actively participates in shaping and legitimising Nigerian English. By foregrounding lexico-semantic Nigerianisms as analytical data, the present study extends existing scholarship beyond thematic and ideological concerns, repositioning the novel as a dynamic linguistic archive.

Methods

This study adopts a qualitative descriptive research design, focusing on the lexico-semantic analysis of Nigerianisms in Lola Shoneyin's *The Secret Lives of Baba Segi's Wives*. Data were collected from the text through close reading and identification of instances of Nigerianisms. A purposive sampling technique was employed to select excerpts that clearly exemplify lexico-semantic variation. A total of twenty-one excerpts were selected for analysis. The selection of twenty-one excerpts is considered sufficient for qualitative analysis, as the study prioritises depth of interpretation over quantitative generalisation. The excerpts were chosen based on their representativeness, clarity, and relevance to the analytical categories. The orientation in this study treats the literary text as a structured representation of socially meaningful language variation (Toolan, 2009), allowing for the examination of how linguistic choices serve as indices of social context.

The data were analysed using a hybrid framework based on Adegbija's (1989) and Bamiro's (1994) linguistic categorisation for lexicosemantic categorisation in Nigerian English, enabling classification into semantic extension, coinage, calquing, and borrowing. This combined approach is adopted to balance conceptual breadth with analytical precision. On the one hand, Adegbija's (1989) five-category model: transfer, analogy, acronyms, semantic shift or extension, and coinage, provides a macro-level descriptive foundation for identifying Nigerianisms as systematic outcomes of linguistic indigenisation. On the other hand, Bamiro's (1994) taxonomy extends this foundational model by offering a more fine-grained, process-oriented categorisation that distinguishes phenomena such as loanshift, semantic underdifferentiation, translation equivalents, ellipsis, and lexico-semantic redundancy.

Data Analysis and Discussion

Semantic Extension in Social Relations

The use of familial terms in the excerpts operates as a form of semantic extension, whereby kinship labels such as aunty, uncle, or sister are extended beyond their biological reference to function as socially indexical markers. In Nigerian English, these terms encode culturally salient distinctions such as age, respect, familiarity, and social hierarchy. Rather than serving purely referential functions, they perform important pragmatic roles, signalling relational positioning between interlocutors.

*Excerpt 1: A young woman sitting outside on a bar stool called to me,
"Aunty, cool yourself down with a bag of cold water." Pg 106*

Excerpt 1 presents a social interaction where the word "Aunty" is used to refer to someone who is not familial. The lexical item "Aunty" is classified as a case of semantic extension. It is used by a young woman sitting on a bar stool to address Bolanle, an unrelated older woman, thereby signalling respect and social hierarchy. Its closest Standard British English equivalents are "Madam" or "Miss." Thus, the extension of "Aunty" from a familial term to a general honorific for an older or higher-status female is an example of how Nigerian English reorganises the semantic field of address terms to align with indigenous sociocultural norms. In the market context (p. 106), the young vendor's use of "Aunty" performs a social act that acknowledges Bolanle's perceived social superiority (as educated) and attempts to invoke the obligations and familiarity of kinship. This usage indexes a Nigerian communicative ethos where social interactions are routinely framed within an extended family model to engender respect and smooth interaction. This is a function absent in the generic BrE through the use of "Miss" or "Madam."

Excerpt 2: Sister, it is this wife of mine who needs your help. Pg 33

In Excerpt 2, the lexical item “Sister” is similarly classified as a semantic extension. It is used by Baba Segi to address a nurse, mapping an institutional role onto a kinship category. In Standard British English, “Nurse” would be the appropriate term. Baba Segi’s address of the nurse as “Sister” (p. 33) serves a crucial characterising and world-building function. This extension reveals his traditional, semi-literate worldview, where formal institutional roles are understood through the familiar perspective of kinship and community roles. By using “Sister,” the text characterises Baba Segi’s persona as a man who translates the impersonal, clinical space of a hospital into a social terrain. This choice also instantly authenticates the Nigerian setting that signals to the reader a healthcare environment where such a familiar address is normative, thus reinforcing the novel’s cultural specificity. The implication is that the lexical choice in the excerpt extends kinship terms into professional domains to reinforce cultural norms of familiarity and respect.

Semantic extension and coinage for euphemistic expressions

Semantic extension also functions as a euphemistic strategy, allowing speakers to stretch existing lexical items beyond their conventional meanings in order to express sensitive or culturally delicate concepts. In this context, words are resemanticised to encode meanings related to sexuality, reproduction, or bodily processes in ways that are indirect yet culturally intelligible. This process reflects a pragmatic need to avoid explicit or potentially offensive terminology, particularly in contexts governed by norms of modesty and decorum.

*Excerpt 3: Baba Segi only comes to **deposit his seed** in my womb. (Page 43)*

In Excerpt 3, “Seed” is classified as a metaphorical semantic extension. The Standard British English equivalent is “semen”, employing an agricultural metaphor to describe reproduction. It uses the word to avoid sexual explicitness in conversation. The shift from “semen” to “seed” (p. 43) can be considered both euphemistic and metaphorical (Lakoff & Johnson, 1980). It maps an agricultural source domain onto the target-domain of human reproduction. The domain of agriculture is brought onto human fertility to reflect a traditional, often patriarchal, understanding of procreation where the man provides the essential, generative “seed” planted in the receptive “soil” of the womb. Iya Segi’s usage, while resentful, employs this culturally entrenched metaphor. The choice of “seed” over the clinical “semen” lexicalises a specific cultural model of fertility, which is a central theme in the novel. It demonstrates how Nigerian English can retain the conceptual frameworks of indigenous languages, using the resources of English to express a distinctly non-Western understanding of the body and kinship. In other words, semantic extension facilitates culturally resonant and euphemistic expression.

*Excerpt 4: I can't do this! There is only one way for a man to **shed body water**, and that is the way I have done it all my life. (pg 191)*

The coinage “body-water” (p. 191) in Excerpt 4 operates on multiple levels to indicate euphemistic extension referring to sexual release. It refers to ejaculation, with “ejaculate” as its Standard English equivalent. Like Excerpt 3, it functions as a culturally specific expression that is more concrete and physiologically descriptive than the word “ejaculate.” Its semantic frame is one of substance and loss (“shed”), contrasting with the more clinical or performative frames of BrE equivalents. Second, its use by Baba Segi in a moment of defensive crisis is noteworthy. It is not merely a Nigerianism but a marker of his idiolect and psychological state. His insistence on the “one way” to shed it defends his masculine identity and potency against

medicalised challenge. The term itself, with its tangible, almost elemental quality, reinforces his traditional, non-scientific worldview, making his confrontation with modern medicine (and Bolanle's infertility) not just personal but epistemic.

Neologisms for Cultural Specificity

Neologism in Nigerian English represents a process of lexical innovation driven by the need to encode culturally specific realities that lack direct equivalents in Standard British English. Through coinage, lexical items or compound forms that capture the nuances of indigenous social practices, material culture and identity markers are presented.

Excerpt 5: Iya Segi yanked her head tie off her head and flung it across the room yelling, 'why kill innocent children.' (Pg 12)

In excerpt 5, "Head-tie" is presented as a neologistic coinage which refers to a culturally specific head covering associated with identity and social status. The Standard English equivalent, "headscarf," lacks this cultural specificity. The excerpt narrates how Iya Segi yanked her headscarf off to show how shocked she was about the news cast on the television. The coinage "head-tie" (p. 12) is an example of cultural lexicalisation, where a generic English term "headscarf" is rejected in favour of a more precise, culturally-loaded neologism. A "headscarf" denotes a functional item of clothing intricately tied to notions of femininity, marital status, occasion, and social pride. When Iya Segi "yanked her head-tie off," the action carries a symbolic weight that a "headscarf" could not. This gesture is one of emotional disarray and a deliberate unmasking and abandonment of social decorum. The coinage, therefore, invokes its entire cultural semiotics and its role as an extension of a woman's public persona. Its use in the narrative treats this cultural knowledge as a given, seamlessly integrating it into the English text and arguing for its necessity within the Nigerian English lexicon. It encodes evaluative meanings through vivid imagery to richly describe a physical attribute.

*Excerpt 6: Why must she follow her **long throat** wherever it beckons?
Page 93*

"Long throat" is classified as a calque that denotes greed or excessive desire, corresponding to "greed" in Standard English. The excerpt, made by Iya Lara, cautions against covetousness. "Long throat" (p. 93) operates as a moral diagnostic expression. The metaphor deployed in this sense connects the physical attribute of a long throat (capable of swallowing much) to the abstract domain of desire, specifically immoderate, envious, or gluttonous craving. Unlike the more neutral or psychologically abstract "covetousness" or "greed," the use of "long throat" conjures an almost grotesque, animalistic image, making the vice viscerally apparent. In the novel's context, as used by Iya Lara, it functions as an act of condemnation and warning. It diagnoses a character flaw as a physical, almost uncontrollable appetite that leads one astray ("wherever it beckons"). This coinage exemplifies how Nigerian English creates compact, proverb-like phrases that embed a specific cultural morality and a vivid, memorable critique within a novel lexical form.

Intensification through Lexical Redundancy

Lexical redundancy in Nigerian English operates as a form of semantic intensification, where apparent duplication is employed to reinforce meaning, clarify reference, or enhance expressive force. This pattern often arises from the transfer of structures in indigenous languages, where redundancy serves important communicative functions, including disambiguation and rhetorical reinforcement.

Excerpt 7: I looked at them and sniggered knowing their father's fathers could not have a fraction of the wealth I had accumulated. Pg 98

The compound "father's father" (p. 98) in Excerpt 7 reveals an instance of a grammatical and semantic nativisation that indexes a specific kinship ideology. While "grandfather" is a consolidated, reciprocal term in Standard English, the Nigerian English coinage opts for a relational descriptor that explicitly traces lineage through the male line. In many Nigerian cultures, kinship ties are precise. Thus, the excerpt specifies paternal lineage, reflecting the transfer of kinship precision from indigenous languages. When Nigerians speak English, they naturally carry over this logical, precise structure from their mother tongues. Thus, "Grandfather" as a term could be ambiguous, as it could mean one's father's father or one's mother's father. Thus, the use of "father's father" is a deliberate and logical adaptation of English to serve the needs of a culture where precise kinship ties are paramount. It solves the ambiguity inherent in the English word "grandfather" by applying a structural pattern borrowed from Nigerian languages. The coinage, therefore, does the cultural work of foregrounding patrilineality. It is a linguistic artefact that carries within it a worldview where the "father's father" is a more significant social category than the generic "grandfather," emphasising continuity, inheritance, and male ancestral authority.

Transfer and Translation of indigenous thought

Underlying metaphors and thought patterns are mapped onto English expressions to create a variety of English that is uniquely configured to express a Nigerian reality. This process involves mapping underlying metaphors, idioms, and conceptual frameworks from local languages onto English lexical and syntactic forms. As a result, expressions in Nigerian English frequently reflect indigenous worldviews, including communal orientations, embodied metaphors, and culturally specific modes of reasoning. These translated structures may appear unconventional from a Standard English perspective, but they are internally coherent and semantically rich within their cultural context.

Excerpt 8: Thank you for returning our mouths to the matter at hand, my friend. Page 5

Excerpt 8 was from Baba Segi, thanking Olaopa for drawing back their attention to what was being discussed. This calque is a pragmatic remapping that translates a Yoruba (or Nigerian Pidgin) conceptualisation of speech as a physical, communal act. Instead of the mental-focused "drawing back our attention," the phrase embodies cognition and dialogue. "Mouths" are the instruments of collective discussion; to "return" them is to physically reorient the group's shared speech-act towards a focal point. This indexes a sociocultural model of communication that is collective, contrasting with the more individualistic, psychological model of the Standard English equivalent.

Excerpt 9: Then one day, as mama sat in the front yard wrinkling her nose, the babies would leak down her leg.

In the excerpt, Femi was talking about how his mother ate a lot of peppers, which would eventually lead to premature birth. Premature birth is the Standard English equivalent. This expression deploys the use of metaphor to map the source domain of liquid/substance loss onto the target domain of miscarriage or premature birth. The expression avoids the clinical terminologies "miscarry" or "abort" and instead employs an image that conveys suddenness, helplessness, and a sense of wasted potential. It demystifies and concretises a traumatic event within a specific cultural lexicon of the body. This translation helps maintain the euphemistic

sense of the situation, and it authentically represents a traditional, non-medicalised narrative of reproductive misfortune.

*Excerpt 10: Ah! "Wisdom at last", Iya Segi said. When Bolanle fails to give him a child baba Segi will **throw her out**. Pg 50*

The expression in Excerpt 10 as regards "throw her out" specifically means to divorce or repudiate a wife, with the strong implication that she is being sent away from the matrimonial home, often to return to her parents' house. "Throw her out" translates a conception of marriage as a patriarchal proprietorship within a polygamous system, where a wife's failure to fulfil a core duty (childbearing) justifies unilateral expulsion from the household. Iya Segi's use of this phrase menacingly frames Bolanle's potential fate as an act of domestic disposal. The Standard English "divorce" implies a legal process with potential bilateral agency. The phrase "give him a child" is another example of a culturally-loaded semantic translation in Nigerian English to imply "conceive."

*Excerpt 11: Iya Femi **picked me up with her eyes and threw me to the floor**. Pg 55*

The excerpt is a speech made by Iya Tope, explaining how disgustingly Iya Segi looked at her. This expression translates a phrase where a malevolent gaze is conceptualised as having physical, violent force. It extends the semantic domain of body parts ("eyes") to function as instruments of kinetic action ("pick up," "throw"). It conveys the totalizing and destabilising psychological impact of Iya Femi's glare, rendering the experience as a physical assault. It showcases how richly experiential and emotional language is created, where Standard English might be expressed through abstraction or understatement.

Direct Borrowing for Semantic Untranslatability

Direct borrowing occurs when lexical items from Nigerian indigenous languages are incorporated into English without translation, typically because they encode meanings that are semantically untranslatable or culturally dense. In such cases, borrowing preserves both the semantic integrity and cultural authenticity of the term.

*Excerpt 12: The greetings done with, Baba Segi raised his arms so his **agbada** could be prised off by Iya Segi's fingers. Pg 8*

In Excerpt 12, the borrowing of *agbada* (p. 8) is a case of referential necessity due to cultural specificity. The SBrE gloss "clothes" is a reduction. An *agbada* captures status, occasion, masculinity, and Yoruba/Nigerian identity that the use of "clothes" cannot convey. Its elaborate embroidery and ceremonial method of wearing carry specific social meanings. Shoneyin uses the indigenous term to preserve this full semantic and semiotic load. This borrowing points to the fact that certain cultural artefacts require their original names to travel intact into English, demanding their own entry in an NE dictionary as culturally key terms.

*Excerpt 13: He pulled the stool towards his crotch and proceeded to **demolish the mountain of amala**. Page 9*

Amala was borrowed from the Yoruba language into the English language to refer to food in the above excerpt. Translating *amala* (p. 9) as "food," "dumpling," or even "paste" may erase its experiential uniqueness. *Amala*, made from yam flour, has a distinct texture, colour, swallowing technique, and accompanying soups. Baba Segi "demolishing a mountain" of it is a culturally precise image of consumption tied to status and appetite. This borrowing reflects how culinary lexicons are often the most resistant to translation, as taste and foodways are core

to cultural identity. The use of amala grounds the narrative. It demonstrates that NE borrows objects for specific embodied experiences that generic English terms cannot index.

*Excerpt 14: She wants to kill my father with **juju** before he walks me down the aisle! Page 58*

This is an important borrowing that imports an entire epistemic framework. Translating juju (p. 58) as "charm" is profoundly inadequate. "Charm" suggests a minor, often benign, object. Juju encompasses a complex system of spiritual power, magic, witchcraft, and metaphysical intervention that can be used for protection or harm. The character's accusation, "kill my father with juju," carries the weight of a specific cultural diagnosis of malice that "charm" could not convey. This borrowing shows how NE integrates terms for which there is no cognitive or cultural equivalent in the Standard English worldview. It forces the language to accommodate an alien epistemic category, making juju a crucial, untranslatable loanword central to understanding characters' motivations and fears.

Conclusion

This study has examined Nigerianisms in *The Secret Lives of Baba Segi's Wives* as instances of lexico-semantic variation within Nigerian English. Through the analysis of fourteen excerpts, the study identified four major processes: semantic extension, neologistic coinage, calquing, and direct borrowing. Through semantic extension, existing English words are adapted to express culturally specific meanings, particularly in domains such as kinship, social relations, and embodied experience. Calquing reflects the structural transfer of indigenous thought patterns into English, while borrowing preserves lexical items that encode culturally bound concepts for which no direct equivalents exist. Coinage further expands the lexicon by naming locally salient phenomena. The analysis reveals that these lexico-semantic processes are patterned and interpretable within their sociocultural context, reinforcing the view of Nigerian English as a structured variety with its own internal logic.

This analysis demonstrates that literary discourse can serve as a viable site for examining patterned linguistic variation. Nigerianisms are markers of a traditional, proverb-laden, and orally-shaped worldview, which Shoneyin uses to authenticate their cultural grounding and emotional expressiveness. The use of Nigerianisms in the text directly addresses what Bamgboṣe (1998) calls the "communicative gap" in Standard English for the Nigerian experience. Some lexemes have no precise BrE equivalents because they denote cultural realities absent from the British context. They fail to capture the required specific style and social connotations, necessitating the legitimisation of components of the NE lexicon. By integrating these terms seamlessly into her narrative, Shoneyin performs their normalisation. These shifts reveal how NE reorganises the semantic field of English to align with indigenous epistemologies. The central point is that these Nigerianisms are not errors relative to an external standard. Rather, they constitute a coherent, socially-indexical system that is vital for authentic literary representation and everyday communication in Nigeria. The novel serves as a microcosm of Nigerian sociolinguistic life that demonstrates how lexico-semantic variation is patterned by factors such as education, gender, and tradition.

The implications of this study lie in its contribution to ongoing discussions in World Englishes by providing a focused account of how Nigerianisms function at the lexico-semantic level. Rather than treating these forms as peripheral or stylistic, the analysis demonstrates that they are systematic and patterned features of Nigerian English, particularly in domains such as kinship, social relations, material culture, and belief systems. The study also underscores the value of literary texts, such as *The Secret Lives of Baba Segi's Wives*, as sites for observing

naturally occurring language variation in context. By showing how localised lexical forms operate within dialogue and narration, it highlights the role of literary discourse in reflecting and shaping everyday language use. In this way, the study contributes to a more precise understanding of how meaning is extended and structured in Nigerian English, without recourse to external evaluative standards.

References

- Adegbija, E. (1989). Lexico-Semantic variation in Nigerian English. *World Englishes* 8(2),165-177
- Adenigbo, A., & Alugbin, M. (2020). A satirical reading of Wole Soyinka's a play of giants. *International Journal of Literature and Arts*, 8(6), 320-325.
- Bamgbose, A. (1998). Torn between the norms: Innovations in world Englishes. *World Englishes*, 17, 1–14.
- Bamiro, E. O. (1994). Lexico-semantic variation in Nigerian English. *World Englishes*, 13(1), 47-60.
- Banjo, A (1982). Towards a definition of standard Nigerian spoken English. *Acts de congress de la societe*,105-176
- Eze, C. (2015). Feminist empathy: Unsettling African cultural norms in the secret lives of Baba Segi's wives. *African Studies*, 74(3), 310-326.
- Idowu-Faith, B. O. (2016). Critical stylistics and the politics of male characterisation in Lola Shoneyin's the secret lives of Baba Segi's wives. In A. Odebunmi, A. Osisanwo, H. Bodunde & S. Ekpe (Eds.), *Grammar, applied linguistics, and society* (pp. 393-409). Obafemi Awolowo University Press.
- Jowitt, D. (1991). *Nigerian English usage: An introduction*. Longman.
- Kachru, B. B. (1985). Standards, codification and sociolinguistic realism: The English language in the outer circle. In R. Quirk & H. Widdowson (Eds.), *English in the world* (pp.11 - 30). Cambridge University Press.
- Lakoff, G., & Johnson, M. (1980). *Metaphors we live by*. University of Chicago Press.
- Moolla, F. F. (2017). The polygynous household in Lola Shoneyin's the secret lives of Baba Segi's Wives: A haven in a heartless world. *Ariel A Review of International English Literature*, 48(1), 71-96.
- Nyuykighan, M. D. (2025). Unveiling the Dark Underbelly of Polygamy in Lola Shoneyin's The Secret Lives of Baba Segi's Wives. *International Journal of Language and Literary Studies*, 7(2), 82-98.
- Sapir, E. (1963). *Language: An introduction to the study of speech*. London: Rupert Hart-Davies.
- Schneider, E. W. (2007). *Postcolonial English: Varieties around the world*. Cambridge University Press.
- Shoneyin, L. (2010). *The Secret Lives of Baba Segi's Wives*. Nigeria: Cassava Republic Press.
- Toolan, M. (2009). *Narrative: A critical linguistic introduction*. Routledge.